

SCALEDDEM

Social Media Code of Conduct

The ScaleDem project promotes democratic practices and participatory governance. Therefore, we think social media should be a place of positive exchange. This includes the comment section of our posts. For this reason, we have adopted a social media code of conduct.

In particular, ScaleDem will not allow any type of content considered as:

- hate speech
- bullying or harassment
- insults, threats or personal attacks
- promoting violence
- sexually explicit
- targeting any group based on race, ethnicity, religion, sexual identity or gender identity with offensive terms
- spam (promoting any product or similar)
- false or misleading information

Comments found to be in violation of the code of conduct will be deleted, and the commenter may be permanently banned from posting on ScaleDem's social media accounts.